

The new Stage of development with E-music classes and E-concerts

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Abstract

Music education including e-music teaching, and e-music concerts that are offered by several learning portals can be regarded as progress within music. It is a very innovative development that has promoted easier accessibility of music education and performance across the globe. Independent musicians can easily reach global recognition via an inevitable and equalizer tool – the internet. Technology has facilitated many musicians and tutors to connect with more people so as to exhibit their talents. In today's time, it is easy to use several available platforms to broadcast from one and many viewers can watch the concert at their convenience. The main objective of the paper is to analyse the inclusion of such new ways and advancement in music education as well as performance. It also analyses the conventional methodologies that are used and the impact and effects of technology on it. The methodology used in this paper is both qualitative and quantitative. Methods inculcated are surveys, personal interviews and other sources of available data with an indication of what impact this revolution has made on music performance and learning. In light of digital platforms and communication technologies, emerging musicians have experienced an enormous increase in learning and music concert opportunities. Therefore this study seeks to explore the use of mediums like Zoom, Google Meet and Skype among others that have transformed the traditional scenario of Hindustani classical music, which has broadened audience reach, widened accessibility, and made room for new young performers. In addition, it also illustrates new pathways and enhancements capable of supporting further learning experiences.

Keywords: Digital Platforms, music education, E-classes, and E-concerts.

Research Paper

Introduction

Hindustani classical music is an old, living art form that has deep cultural resonance with the Indian sub-continent. The complex arrangements, superb spontaneity as well as the deep bonding of the listeners are features this music is renowned for. Many prospective artists have struggled with the limitations that come with traditional face-to-face or physical interaction learning and practising of Hindustani classical music (Sambamoorthy 81).

The introduction of E-Music classes and E-Concerts in the post-pandemic period has remarkably changed the Hindustani classical music scenario. Such digital platforms and communication technologies provide new avenues for learning, cooperation and presentation, making the emerging artist's tasks easier than ever before. The purpose of this article is to focus on various avenues by which music education and performances have been advantaged using digital spaces.

Traditional Hindustani Classical Music: Challenges and Limitations

Learning Hindustani classical music entailed being close enough to accomplished gurus and also possessing the requisite equipment in the traditional system. (Sambamoorthy 82) The aspirants were limited by a few factors including a lack of famous teachers, their geographic location as well as finances. Lakinen J. and Mantymaki M. in their work on social media and artists, (26) described that with the traditional ways it is difficult for emerging artists to gain market exposure, present and promote their talent. Besides that, competition within the field, few performance opportunities, as well as reigning established artists also made it difficult for upcoming talent to find a niche. (Salo 26)

The Emergence of Digital Platforms and Communication Technologies

Digital platforms and contemporary means of communication have brought a radical change in the

pedagogy of Hindustani classical music. Using the internet, e-music classes allow children to get access to qualified tutors from all parts of the world. (Palneetkar 207)

In a personal interview with Dr. Soma Singh (an exponent of Gwalior gharana), she mentioned that:

“The use of digital platforms in music teaching is a huge advancement. Earlier Indian Classical music could only be learnt in a face-to-face method. After the pandemic, new ways of learning and communication have been developed. This can be helpful for the younger generation. Understanding theoretical concepts has become easier. Ragas can now be learnt at a great convenience. If a student faces any problem in understanding a raga or any other concept, an e-class can be taken at any time and from anywhere for clarity. Although this can't be a full replacement for the traditional Guru-Shishya Parampara, but it can be used as a tool to understand the concepts and keep the continuity in this busy world.” (Singh)

Merging e-music classes is also beneficial, as it provides students with plenty of opportunities to learn through new technology. They are able to select various accredited instructors, have flexible schedules, study independently among others, and get personal attention and guidance where necessary. Technology is also helpful in incorporating multimedia materials such as PowerPoint slides, pictures, videos, and recordings which contribute to better interactive learning. The incorporation of multimedia materials such as images and videos can be easily integrated into other digital platforms like Zoom, Google Meet, Skype, and Google Classroom. It is important to note that these are the current major platforms used for conducting E-Music lessons. (Dutt). These platforms include the capabilities of having video conferences, screen sharing and live communications that make interactions between the students and gurus effortless.

Enriching Learning Experiences through E-Music Classes

Through democratizing E-music classes, music enthusiasts can now have an easy chance to work with famous gurus and maestros beyond physical boundaries or limitations. Now students can have exposure to established artists in the subject area, regardless of distance, thus extending their horizons further and delving deeper into this art genre. In recent days, many websites and apps have been developed that provide virtual instructions in the art of music made by famous

artists. Apart from that, musicians such as Sarod artist Pandit Tejendra Narayan Mazumdar, Tabla maestros, Pandit Swapan Chaudhuri and Ustad Zakir Hussain, and the Hindustani violinist, Kala Ramnath have conducted online classes and workshops over different platforms and have attracted over 5000 students. Such mass classes with students from different region would never have been possible with the traditional ways of music education. (Rucsanda)

Shubha Mudgal ji, Sh. Hariharan ji and many other well-known artists have designed their music courses in Hindustani classical music on various educational applications like Udemy, Artium Academy etc. Other such initiatives have been taken by Ajivasan Academy by Suresh Wadekar ji, The True School of Music and even international institutions like Berklee College of Music in Boston have come up with online workshops and classes to impart knowledge of Indian classical music to students at their home. (Dutt)

E-music classes are convenient as they ensure that learners can pursue their musical ambitions at different times without disrupting their schedules. Additionally, being location-independent makes it unnecessary to travel and therefore makes it possible to do lessons from home.

Online music courses offer personalized and self-paced learning, allowing instruction that suits each student based on his unique abilities and requirements (Schlager 36). Learners also find the option of going back and listening to a previously recorded lesson and practising to their own rhythm convenient. This helps in mastering and understanding the subject better.

Through virtual interactions, it also promote the notion of togetherness in the learners. Working with peers from different cultures and having a chance to be part of a group presentation enhances one's learning adventure. The use of virtual jam sessions enables students to interact with others, exchange ideas, as well as receive feedback, thus establishing a healthy social atmosphere for learning. The huge stride in music education provides space for musicians, artists, students and laymen among others to access our music and its roots. This is a new phase and a new step towards maintaining our Indian culture.

Survey

A Survey was conducted to study the views and impact of online methods used for performing, teaching and learning music. For this, a questionnaire was prepared and sent to 20 music students and performers to collect and analyse the data regarding the same as shown below.

Table 1

Table 2

The descriptive analysis showed that people had high levels of satisfaction with the use of e-learning platforms and online education in general (70%) while only 20% of the respondents were unsatisfied with the digital inclusion in music learning.; 56.6% of the total respondents use digital platforms for taking/giving music classes. 55% of the total people use video conferencing while 27% use virtual classrooms as a medium of learning. While only 1% use online tutorials and forums. (See table 1,2) However, they all thought that online education could bridge the cultural and socio-economic barriers. They also thought that Artistic growth and career opportunities have increased with digitally inclusive teaching and learning. 90% of people agreed that hybrid learning is beneficial for Indian music education. (See Table 3)

Specifically, the study findings proved that music education can be implemented in a better way through the use of digital platforms for learning and performance, thus confirming the first hypothesis. This would provide the teachers with an opportunity that they could use when making more musical exchanges as well as cultural interactions. Online education was found to have certain advantages based on the findings of the study. The first one notes the availability of courses, portability, compatibility, and low expenses for travelling and other requirements of studying on campus. New skills can also be learned because of the adoption of technology.

E-Concerts: A Paradigm Shift in Hindustani Classical Music Performance

The advent of e-concerts has greatly extended the sphere of influence of Hindustani classical music events. The advent of online platforms allows artists to reach audiences from far-flung locations surpassing geo limits. Reaching a larger audience exposes people to different listeners, thus fostering cultural exchange. (Bala)

In the past, artists were restricted by a lot of distance as they had to cover it when travelling to reach different regions. This limitation is eliminated through e-concerts as artists can perform from anywhere and still access global listeners. This allows the saving of time and other resources and creates a chance to collaborate with artists who have different styles, cultures, and backgrounds. Therefore, these online concerts act as channels of cross-cultural interaction, enabling a conversation between the artists and audience members from various countries.

Fusion music can be created between musicians of Hindustani classical and other genres and different cultures. A case study shows a strong online collaboration of the great trio – Ustad Zakir Hussain, Shankar Mahadevan and John McLaughlin in their album named “Is That So” which was released even during the pandemic.

The other significant endeavours of ‘Durga Jasraj ji’ through ‘Art and Artistes’ include India’s audio-video music content displayed globally. Utsah Festival of music and dance by art and artists offers an opportunity to the new generation of musicians while engaging other people through different electronic media. (Singh) Sitar Maestro, Purbayan Chatterjee has done an admirable work of collaborating on recitals and discussions with musicians via different online media.

Many people also follow Varanasi’s annual Sankat Mochan Festival and some of the biggest music festivals which are streamed live on social media platforms. People can now have a chance to go to performances across the country and no longer experience any obstacles created by distance.

Enhancing Performance Opportunities for Budding Artists

Young artists now have more exposure through online performances which provide avenues for the presentation of their talent. Therefore, they can organize their online concerts, develop a global fan base and attract the attention of music lovers, critics as well as professionals. It has increased their visibility which plays an important

role towards their artistic development as well as their general career progression. In digital platforms, budding artists can network with established musicians and mentors. They can make meaningful relationships, seek advice, and get constructive criticism for their artistic development through virtual music lessons and concerts. (Salo 27)

Also, it enables new artists to work with experienced musicians. Performance of the young talents becomes easy in the virtual space where they can perform with popular artists thereby facilitating the development of art and networking in the sphere of the performance arena. This has greatly exposed budding artists to the public view.

Future Implications and Opportunities

There are many possibilities for incorporating AI/VR into a better e-learning and virtual concert experience. The use of AI-tools is capable of giving immediate suggestions to the students with constant feedback. Similarly, VR technology enables it to construct realistic concert sets within the virtual world thus making it an effective medium of audience communication. (Andres)

It goes without saying, however, that the future of Hindustani classical music is a mix of conventional and digital methods. Hybrid learning models have their strengths when it comes to combining face-to-face encounters with the possibilities that come with online applications for a more versatile approach toward education. (Schlager 36-38) Likewise, a mixture of real and virtual factors can be utilized for creating hybrid shows which tend to be outstanding and engaging musical events.

Music lessons online may remove social and cultural boundaries (Rucsanda and Bolibou 73). In order to ensure that all aspiring artists are afforded an equal opportunity in accessing digital resources, diversity inclusion should be emphasized to make it possible for the promotion of Hindustani classical music as a global art. These improvements will help Hindustani classical music stay alive and keep attracting foreign audiences while preserving its cultural heritage.

Conclusion

The advent of E-Music classes and E-Concerts transformed the sphere of Hindustani classical music

benefiting the musicians in great measure. It has also proven to be a blessing to musicians as well as people who like this type of music since it enabled them to develop Hindustani classical music with digital platforms. It offers unfathomable exposure to Hindustani classical music and enhanced communication between the audience and the performers. Collaboration among musicians has been enhanced by it. These developments have been facilitated through several digital platforms which will continue to be critical in the future of Hindustani classical music.

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